

Applied Partial Differential Variational Techniques

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Abstract

We review and present examples for two new image processing methods based on scale space evolution under partial differential operators. These operators arise from minimizing variational objective functions and from a novel approach that respects the discrete nature of real images.

The first method considered is a variational approach (developed by Hewer et al.) that provides a closed-form expression for the optimal boundary function. This method gives good results with a 2-norm penalty term for approximation error and a 1-norm smoothness term; in this case there is a strong connection with total variation methods.

The second method is a peer group averaging approach (developed by Hewer et al.) that smooths the image without blurring edges. This is accomplished by averaging over window pixels with nearly the same intensity; these pixels are the 'peer group' of the window's central pixel. The direct correspondence between the object characteristics and the parameters of peer group size and window diameter make the parameter selection easier for peer group averaging than for standard variational methods.

These methods are used in combination with PGA providing the initial approximation for the variational descent procedure. This is applied to real image examples and compared to existing methods including a new level-set histogram modification method (developed by Caselles et al.) that treats connected level-sets of pixels as individual units.

1 Introduction

Physical systems governed by partial differential equations have been studied for over 100 years. These equations provide predictions about the future state of the system and the form of these equations allows one to determine system properties such as conservation of energy for Hamiltonian systems. Recent work in image processing has tried to reverse this procedure:

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the desired evolution properties are selected and from these properties the corresponding PDE is generated. Applying this PDE to the original image generates a scale space decomposition with the PDE 'time' parameter playing the role of scale.

The standard way to do this is set up an objective function $E = E(g, u, B)$ that depends on the original image g as well as an approximation u and a boundary function B . Typically E contains a penalty term that measures the difference between g and u , another penalty term for the nonsmoothness in u and also a penalty term for the length of the boundaries of the regions in the image. This latter term is needed to control the number of region components in the final segmentation: too many components and the result is not useful. This is the variational approach in which we chose the form of the objective functional and then use some method to find minimizers u and B for E .

A variety of methods have been developed to implement this approach. These include region merging schemes used by Koepfler and others [5], [6], applying homotopy type methods to the objective function in order to guarantee convergence of descent methods to global minimizers such as the GNC approach of Blake and Zisserman [1], and using the Euler-Lagrange PDE associated with the objective function with the boundary B interpreted as a continuous function rather than a binary process. For general references to variational methods and PDEs related to image processing see [7] and [13].

Each of these approaches has advantages and disadvantages. For example, region merging generally produces excellent results and is easily adapted to a multi-channel form that can accept multiresolution or multispectral image data as input; however region merging can be computationally intensive and may not be appropriate for real-time applications. In fact the computational speed issue applies to almost every variational method. Time considerations place limitations on the number of iterations that can be used in steepest descent procedures. This also means that we must usually forego the luxury of finding the global mini-

mizer of the objective functional and instead seek an approximation that is acceptable rather than optimal.

In this paper we describe two new methods in this area that when combined rapidly generate good approximations. The basic idea in this combination is to use one method to quickly generate an initial approximation u_0 that is close to the desired final approximation u . The second method is then used to refine the initial approximation using only a few descent steps for the objective function. As a byproduct of this descent we also obtain the boundary function associated with the approximation. The objective function we use is described in the next section and gives the boundary function in closed form; this is followed by a description of the peer group averaging method. PGA provides excellent initial approximations u_0 whose properties are controllable by varying the window size and peer group number.

The combined procedure is then tested on a set of real images and compared with existing methods.

2 Variational Approximation and Boundary Description

A general variational framework for image segmentation and approximation is presented in [3]. In addition to several new results, the work in [3] simplifies and systematizes approaches that had previously been considered separately. [8], [9], [10]

A standard approach [8], [9], [10] to segmenting and approximating an image g over a pixel set Ω consists of finding an approximation u and a boundary set K that minimizes an objective functional of the form

$$\tilde{E} = \int_{\Omega \setminus K} w_1(Au - g)^2 + w_2 \|\nabla u\|^2 + \int_K d\sigma$$

where the last integral term corresponds to the length of the boundary. The scalars w_1 and w_2 are weighting factors that determine respectively how closely u approximates g and the smoothness of u . Functionals of this type are often referred to as a Mumford-Shah functionals. See [7] p.24, [8], [9] and [10] for details.

For reasons discussed in [3], we may wish to specify boundaries with a function B taking continuous values between 0 and 1. To accommodate a continuous boundary function B , the Mumford-Shah functional can be recast as

$$E = \int_{\Omega} (w_1(Au - g)^2 + w_2 \|\nabla u\|^2) (1 - B)^2 + B^2. \quad (1)$$

The work in [3] focuses on minimizing a wide class of objective functionals. A closed form solution is derived in [3] for the optimal boundary function B

associated with a given approximation function u : $B = r/(1 + r)$, where r is the residual of the objective function. For example, for the Mumford-Shah functional (1), $r = w_1(u - g)^2 + w_2 \|\nabla u\|^2$. The explicit form of the boundary function can then be used to reduce the objective function to a form in which the minimization problem can be recast as a PDE. The general framework of [3] allows one to compare different objective functions of the Mumford-Shah or Geman type for least squares (L_2 norm) approximation or the total variation (L_1 norm) approach of Osher and Rudin [11], [12]. The numerical results for this paper were obtained using the mixed norm objective functional

$$E = \int_{\Omega} (w_1(Au - g)^2 + w_2 \|\nabla u\|) (1 - B)^2 + B^2.$$

We used the 1-norm for the smoothness term ∇u since this produced sharper edges in the approximation u than the 2-norm. Note that to avoid discontinuous derivatives at $\nabla u = 0$ we use the modified smoothness term $(\nabla u \cdot \nabla u + \delta)^{1/2}$ instead of $\|\nabla u\|$. With this modification, the Euler-Lagrange descent method for this objective functional yields the following PDE. For a given approximation u of g , define the residual

$$r = w_1(u - g)^2 + w_2(\nabla u \cdot \nabla u + \delta)^{1/2},$$

then the descent PDE for u is given by

$$u_t = \frac{2w_1(g - u)}{(1 + r)^2} + w_2 \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\nabla u}{(1 + r)^2} (\nabla u \cdot \nabla u + \delta)^{-1/2} \right)$$

subject to the Neumann boundary condition $\partial u / \partial n = 0$ where n is the outward normal.

3 Peer Group Averaging

Peer group image processing identifies a 'peer group' for each pixel from a sliding window and then uses the peer group to make processing decisions at that pixel. A diffusion form of peer group processing was presented in [4] that averages over the peer group (PGA). Two parameters provide direct control over which objects are selectively enhanced: peer group size which corresponds to area (number of pixels in the object), and window diameter (window size needed to enclose the object). The direct correspondence between these parameters and the object characteristics is in sharp contrast to parameter selection for other image processing methods such as variational approaches in which it is unclear how to select good values for the smoothness and approximation weights.

The basic idea consists of two steps: to enhance objects with n or more pixels 1) identify a peer group of

size n for each pixel 2) process the pixel value based on the characteristics of the peer group. There are many ways to select the peer group for a given pixel. In general, peer group members should share common values. For a single image, the peer group may be nearby pixels with similar intensity values. For a sequence of images used in determining optical flow fields, the peer group can be nearby pixels (in time and space) with similar intensity values and similar velocity values. In another context, texture values may be assigned to each pixel and then the peer group determined by nearness in texture space.

The work in [4] analyzed peer group averaging for peer groups based on intensity nearness. The PGA iteration is nonlinear because of the peer group selection. The main result of [4] is that the PGA algorithm converges to an image that is constant on the interior regions of the image.

3.1 PGA and Shock Filtering

In shock filtering [14] [11],[12], intensity values from the interior of regions move outward towards the region edges along gradient lines. The convexity of the intensity along the gradient direction determines the motion direction along the gradient and this direction assignment means that when two regions meet at an edge the image intensity will experience a jump. Thus the edges of the image correspond to stationary shock fronts for this type of image processing.

In shock filtering the maximum values of the image intensity and the minimum values move outward from the interior of their regions to meet at the boundaries. This means that the contrast at the edges is maximized. This also means that shock filtering preserves the total variation of the original image.

Shock filtering smooths in the sense that each region assumes a constant value. However, shock filtering does not remove isolated noise such as salt-and-pepper noise, as discussed by Osher and Rudin in [11].

In its simplest form for 1d signals, shock filtering uses the original signal g as initial data for a nonlinear convection equation: $u_t = -\text{sgn}(u_{xx}) u_x$ with $u(x, 0) = g(x)$. In this formulation we must be careful to form derivative approximations from the appropriate direction. Thus if intensity information is to move from right to left, then we want u_x to represent the righthand derivative and we use a forward difference to approximate u_x . Similarly we use a backward difference if we want intensity information to move from left to right.

Consider a simple Euler update scheme for the shock filter equation: let h be the time step and set $u_i^{new} = u_i + hu_t$. If u is montone increasing at i and

$u_{xx} < 0$ in the sense that $u_{i+1} - 2u_i + u_{i-1} < 0$ then the choice $h = 1/2$ leads to $u_i^{new} = (u_i + u_{i+1})/2$. This is the same result we would get with PGA for a peer group of size $n = 2$ because the convexity condition $u_{i+1} - 2u_i + u_{i-1} < 0$ is the same as $|u_{i+1} - u_i| < |u_i - u_{i-1}|$ when u is montone increasing. Similarly, if $u_{xx} > 0$ the choice $h = 1/2$ in the shock filter Euler update leads to the same result as the PGA update: $u_i^{new} = (u_{i-1} + u_i)/2$.

This intersection of shock filtering and PGA for particular parameter choices means that results for one method apply immediately to the other. For example, PGA with $n = 2$ for signals is total variation preserving because the same is true for shock filtering. However, the two methods are not the same for other choices of parameters. In particular PGA with larger peer group sizes automatically incorporates smoothing over the peer group and is able to handle problems such as the isolated intensity spikes of salt and pepper noise.

4 Numerical Applications

Recently Sapiro and Caselles [15] showed that histogram modification could be viewed as an image deformation process, rather than a simple distribution modification. Following up on this result, Caselles et al. [2] developed a new shape preserving contrast enhancement technique. This method equalizes the histogram of the intensities of the connected components of the level sets of the image. The rationale being that such sets constitute the basic objects in the image and as such should be preserved spatially although it is permissible to change their intensity to enhance contrast.

For the images treated in this section, we applied the PGA algorithm to the original image g for 3 iterations using a 3x3 window and peer group number $n = 6$. (This choice preserves binary half-planes, however other choices are useful such as $n = 3$ which preserves lines or $n = 4$ which preserves corners. See [4] for more details.) The resulting approximation u_0 was then used as initial image for the descent procedure described in Section 2 and the final approximation was obtained by using 50 steepest descent steps. The results are shown in Figure 1b with the original image shown in Figure 1a. These are compared with the shape preserving local histogram modification procedure of Caselles et al. in Figures 2.

5 Conclusion

By combining PGA and the variational approach of Hewer et al. in [3] fast approximation and boundary detection is achievable. This method preserves desir-

Figure 1: (a) Original 16-bit image (Top); (b) Final approximation (Center); (c) Boundaries (Bottom).

Figure 2: Histogram modification of original, 16-bit range image.

able features such as edges and corners (depending on the peer group number) while smoothing unwanted detail from the interiors of image regions. The speed of this method does not come at the cost of degraded performance as seen by the comparison with the advanced shape preserving local histogram modification methods developed by Caselles et al.

References

- [1] A. Blake and A. Zisserman, "Visual Reconstruction," MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, 1987.
- [2] V. Caselles, J.L. Lisani, J.M. Morel and G. Sapiro, "Shape Preserving Local Histogram Modification," *Hewlett Packard Technical Report HPL-97-58*, April 1997.
- [3] G. Hewer, C. Kenney and B. Manjunath, "Variational Image Segmentation Using Boundary Functions," *IEEE Trans. Image Processing*, to appear.
- [4] G. Hewer, C. Kenney, B. Manjunath and R. Schoyen, "Peer Group Image Processing," *IEEE Trans. Image Processing*, submitted.
- [5] G. Koepfler, J. M. Morel and S. Solimini, "Segmentation by Minimizing Functionals and the Merging Methods," *IEEE Proc. of the 12th GRETSI Colloque*, 1991.
- [6] G. Koepfler, C. Lopez and L. Rudin, "Data Fusion by Segmentation: Application to Texture Discrimination," *IEEE Proc. of the 14th GRETSI Colloque*, pp. 707-710, Sept. 1993.
- [7] J. Morel and S. Solimini, *Variational Methods in Image Segmentation*, Birkhäuser, Boston, 1995.
- [8] D. Mumford and J. Shah, "Boundary detection by minimizing functionals," *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, San Francisco, 1985.
- [9] D. Mumford and J. Shah, "Boundary detection by minimizing functionals," *Image Understanding*, S. Ullman and W. Richards, eds., 1988.
- [10] D. Mumford and J. Shah, "Optimal approximation by piecewise smooth functions and associated variational problems," *Comm. on Pure and Appl. Math.*, Vol. XLII, No. 4, 1989.
- [11] S. Osher and L. Rudin, "Feature-oriented image enhancement using shock filters," *SIAM J. Numer. Anal.*, vol. 27, pp. 919-940, 1990.
- [12] S. Osher and L. Rudin, "Shocks and other non-linear filtering applied to image processing," *Proceedings SPIE Appl. Dig. Image Proc. XIV*, vol. 1567, pp. 414-430, 1991.
- [13] M. Proesmans, E. Pauwels and L. van Gool, "Coupled Geometry-driven diffusion equations for low-level vision," in *Geometry-Driven Diffusion in Computer Vision*, B.M. ter Harr Romeny, Ed., Kluwer Academic Publ., Boston, 1994, pp. 1991-228.
- [14] L. Rudin, "Images, Numerical Analysis of Singularities, and Shock Filters," Ph.D. thesis, Computer Science Dept., Caltech, Pasadena, CA, Tech. Report 5250:TR:87, 1987.
- [15] G. Sapiro and V. Caselles, "Histogram Modification via Differential Equations," *J. Diff Eqs.*, to appear.